

UNLEASHING THE POWER OF CRITICAL THINKING: A PATHWAY TO INFORMED DECISION MAKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11085129>

Abstract. *In a world increasingly shaped by environmental challenges, the role of critical thinking in hydrology education is paramount. This study, conducted at TIIAME University, focuses on understanding the development and application of critical thinking skills among hydrology students. Through qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys, the research investigates students' experiences, perceptions, and engagement with critical thinking within the hydrology curriculum.*

Keywords: *analytical skills, problem-solving, interdisciplinary collaboration, experiential learning, curriculum enhancement, environmental challenges, water management, educational interventions*

Annotatsiya. *Dunyo muhim muammolari tomonidan ko'zda tutilgan odamlar uchun, kritik fikrlashning suv texnologiyalari ta'limida o'rin olgan roli juda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu tadqiqot, TIIAME Universitetida amalga oshirilgan, suv texnologiyalari talabalarining kritik fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish va qo'llashni tushunchalari, ma'qullari va kritik fikrlash bilan bo'lishgan taalluqlarini o'rganadi.*

Аннотация. *В мире, все более формируемом экологическими вызовами, роль критического мышления в образовании по гидрологии является важнейшей. Это исследование, проведенное в Университете ТИАМЕ, фокусируется на понимании развития и применения навыков критического мышления среди студентов гидрологии. Через качественные интервью и количественные опросы исследование изучает опыт, восприятия и вовлеченность студентов в критическое мышление в рамках учебного плана по гидрологии.*

Introduction:

In today's world, where information is readily available at every turn, critical thinking becomes the key to dissecting complex situations and making informed decisions. This section introduces the topic of critical thinking and explains its significance in contemporary society.

Methods:

Critical thinking encompasses a multifaceted approach to cognitive processing, requiring a combination of analytical skills, evaluative techniques, and inferential reasoning. This study employed a mixed-methods approach to explore the development and application of critical thinking skills across diverse contexts.

Qualitative Phase: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with individuals known for their adept critical thinking skills. Participants were selected from various professional backgrounds, including academia, business, and public service, to capture a broad spectrum of perspectives. The interviews focused on participants' experiences with critical thinking, strategies for cultivating it, and perceived impacts on decision-making and problem-solving.

Quantitative Phase: A survey instrument was designed to assess self-reported levels of critical thinking ability among a representative sample of individuals from different demographic groups. The survey included items measuring participants' confidence in their critical thinking

skills, frequency of engaging in critical thinking activities, and perceived barriers to effective critical thinking.

Data Analysis: Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis techniques to identify recurring themes and patterns related to critical thinking experiences and outcomes. Quantitative data from the survey were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize participants' responses and inferential statistics to examine relationships between critical thinking variables and demographic factors.

Results: The qualitative analysis revealed several key findings regarding the development and application of critical thinking skills. Participants emphasized the importance of exposure to diverse perspectives, active engagement with complex problems, and reflection on one's own thinking processes. They also highlighted the role of formal education, lifelong learning, and collaborative dialogue in fostering critical thinking abilities.

In the quantitative analysis, survey results indicated significant variation in self-reported levels of critical thinking ability across demographic groups. Younger participants reported higher levels of confidence in their critical thinking skills, while older participants expressed greater frequency of engaging in critical thinking activities. Gender differences were also observed, with females reporting higher levels of perceived barriers to effective critical thinking compared to males.

In the context of TIAME University, focusing on hydrology students, the research delved into understanding the development and application of critical thinking skills within this specific academic domain.

Qualitative Findings:

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with hydrology students at TIAME University to explore their experiences with critical thinking. The interviews revealed several noteworthy insights into the cultivation and utilization of critical thinking skills within the hydrology curriculum.

Participants highlighted the significance of practical fieldwork experiences, laboratory exercises, and research projects in honing their critical thinking abilities. They emphasized the importance of applying theoretical knowledge to real-world hydrological problems, engaging in collaborative problem-solving activities, and seeking feedback from faculty mentors to enhance their analytical skills.

Additionally, participants discussed the role of interdisciplinary perspectives in enriching their critical thinking processes. They emphasized the value of integrating insights from related fields such as geology, climatology, and environmental science to develop holistic approaches to hydrological analysis and decision-making.

Quantitative Findings:

A survey was administered to hydrology students at TIAME University to assess self-reported levels of critical thinking ability and the frequency of engaging in critical thinking activities. The survey results provided quantitative data on students' perceptions of their critical thinking skills and the factors influencing their development.

Analysis of the survey data revealed that hydrology students at TIAME University generally reported high levels of confidence in their critical thinking abilities. They indicated frequent engagement in activities such as data analysis, problem-solving, and scientific inquiry, both inside and outside the classroom.

However, the survey also identified areas for improvement, particularly in the realm of interdisciplinary collaboration and communication skills. Students expressed a desire for more opportunities to engage with peers from diverse academic backgrounds and to develop their ability to effectively communicate complex hydrological concepts to non-specialist audiences.

Discussion:

Critical thinking plays a key role in societal development, as it contributes to the formation of informed citizens capable of analyzing information, making conscious decisions, and contributing to the public welfare. This section discusses the significance of critical thinking for modern society and offers recommendations for its development.

The findings from this research offer valuable insights into the development and application of critical thinking skills among hydrology students at TIAME University. The qualitative findings underscore the importance of experiential learning and interdisciplinary perspectives in fostering critical thinking abilities within the hydrology curriculum.

Moreover, the quantitative findings highlight the strengths and areas for improvement in students' self-perceived critical thinking skills. By addressing these areas through targeted educational interventions and curriculum enhancements, TIAME University can further empower hydrology students to become effective critical thinkers and problem solvers in their future careers.

Conclusion:

Critical thinking is not just a skill but a way of thinking that can be developed and improved. Its application enables informed decision-making, effective problem-solving, and ensures intellectual independence. In the modern world, critical thinking becomes an indispensable tool for successful adaptation and development. The study sheds light on the critical role of critical thinking in hydrology education at TIAME University. By nurturing a culture of inquiry, collaboration, and interdisciplinary exploration, TIAME can equip its hydrology students with the analytical skills and mindset necessary to address the complex hydrological challenges of the 21st century.

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